

FicTrac: a visual method for tracking spherical motion and generating fictive animal paths

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Abstract

Studying how animals interface with a virtual reality can further our understanding of how attention, learning and memory, sensory processing, and navigation are handled by the brain, at both the neurophysiological and behavioural levels. To this end, we have developed a novel vision-based tracking system, FicTrac (*Fictive path Tracking* software), for estimating the path an animal makes whilst rotating an air-supported sphere using only input from a standard camera and computer vision techniques. We have found that the accuracy and robustness of FicTrac outperforms a low-cost implementation of a standard optical mouse-based approach for generating fictive paths. FicTrac is simple to implement for a wide variety of experimental configurations and, importantly, is fast to execute, enabling real-time sensory feedback for behaving animals. We have used FicTrac to record the behaviour of tethered honeybees, *Apis mellifera*, whilst presenting visual stimuli in both open-loop and closed-loop experimental paradigms. We found that FicTrac could accurately register the fictive paths of bees as they walked towards bright green vertical bars presented on an LED arena. Using FicTrac, we have demonstrated closed-loop visual fixation in both the honeybee and the fruit fly, *Drosophila melanogaster*, establishing the flexibility of this system. FicTrac provides the experimenter with a simple yet adaptable system that can be combined with electrophysiological recording techniques to study the neural mechanisms of behaviour in a variety of organisms, including walking vertebrates.

Keywords: visual tracking, fictive path, spherical treadmill, visual fixation, webcam, *Apis mellifera*

1. Introduction

Deciphering the neural mechanisms of behaviour requires not only experimental paradigms that allow fine control of sensory stimuli, but also carefully calibrated measurement systems that can reliably and accurately indicate an animal's behavioural response. Experiments in which the animal is free to move – either by walking or flying – about an enclosure may permit naturalistic behaviours, but it is very difficult to precisely control the sensory input received by the animal as well as record the animal's physiological responses. Enabling a tethered animal to navigate through a virtual world offers the most control over sensory stimuli. This approach, however, requires an accurate understanding of the various forces produced by the animal as well as the requisite apparatus to measure them and provide sensory feedback. In the case of animals moving in three dimensions, such as flying or swimming, it is extremely difficult to accurately record the minute roll, pitch, and yaw torques as well as the propulsive forces generated by the animal in order to recreate its full 3D path through a virtual environment (Lindemann et al., 2003; Schilstra and Van Hateren, 1998; Nalbach, 1993; Blondeau, 1981; Straw et al., 2011). An experimental paradigm in which a tethered animal walks upon

a treadmill is advantageous in this regard because it enables the complete motion of the animal to be faithfully represented within a virtual 2D environment. The resulting fictive path is the theoretical path that the animal would have taken if it was walking freely in a two dimensional space.

Early implementations of the tethered walking preparation did not in fact tether the animal, but instead allowed it to walk freely on the surface of a sphere, the rotation of which was controlled using servomotors to keep the animal centred on top of the sphere (Götz and Gambke, 1968; Götz and Wenking, 1973; Kramer, 1976). Tethering the animal in place removes the need for expensive servo-mechanical hardware, but requires free rotation of the sphere, which can be achieved by supporting the sphere on a stream of air (Dahmen, 1980). Rotations of the sphere, induced by movements of the animal, can be detected by positioning rotary encoders in direct mechanical contact with the surface of the sphere (Doherty and Pires, 1987; Ye et al., 1995). A similar approach that avoids inducing drag on the rotating sphere involves using a modified computer mouse to record rotations of the sphere around two orthogonal axes (Lott et al., 2007; Hedwig and Poulet, 2004; Mason et al., 2001). Optical (or laser) computer mouse sensors have proven especially useful for this purpose as they eliminate the need for any mechanical contact with the sphere. Optical mouse sensors are cheap and extremely efficient at transcribing rotations of the sphere to 2D motion vectors but they are not designed to measure the 3rd (rotational) degree of freedom. Multiple optical mouse sensors are required, therefore, to decipher the complete

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3D rotation of the sphere (Seelig et al., 2010; Lee and Zhou, 2004).

Indeed, optical mouse sensors are optimised for use in computer mice. Custom optics, illumination, supporting structures, electronics as well as the software to interpret the data produced by the sensors must therefore be developed to re-purpose them for use within an experimental setup (*e.g.* Seelig et al. (2010)). Additionally, the sensitivity of optical mouse sensors to motion of the sphere can be affected by changes in illumination (Tunwattana et al., 2009) or texture (Minoni and Signorini, 2006), as well as diagonal or radial motion (Palacin et al., 2006). These issues can lead to biases in the measured output that could be difficult to characterise precisely in an experimental setup and may be confused with behavioural traits, making interpretation of the neural and behavioural data difficult at best.

Here we introduce and describe the design and operation of FicTrac (*Fictive path Tracking* software), a novel approach for measuring the three-degrees of freedom (3-DOF) rotations of a track ball using only images captured by an off-the-shelf computer vision camera or webcam. The advantages of FicTrac over a standard optical mouse-based approach are:

1. No custom electronics or software to be implemented by the end-user, which significantly simplifies experimental setup time and cost.
2. Freedom to position the camera anywhere with a view of the experimental enclosure, which reduces clutter around the animal and provides for increased exposure to stimuli.
3. No restrictions on the size of the track ball, which means this system is suitable for a wide variety of animals.
4. The absolute orientation of the track ball is measured independently in each frame, which eliminates the accumulation of errors in FicTrac’s estimate of the orientation of the ball and leads to improved accuracy in the reconstruction of the animal’s fictive path.
5. The full 3D rotation of the sphere is measured inherently.

In this study we use FicTrac to demonstrate visual fixation in the honeybee, *Apis mellifera*. Visual fixation, where the animal subject turns, or attempts to turn, to bring a bright visual stimulus to the centre of its field of view (FOV), is a well-studied closed-loop paradigm for both walking and flying tethered insects (*e.g.* Reiser and Dickinson (2008) and Bahl et al. (2013)). This approach has formed the basis for investigating visual responsiveness, learning and memory, neural mechanisms of visual processing, and motor adaptation in response to visual cues (Götz and Gambke, 1968; Heisenberg and Wolf, 1984). Freely flying honeybees are commonly used to study visual learning and memory (Srinivasan, 2011) and can be trained easily, although closed-loop fixation has been difficult to test with tethered flying honeybees (but see Luu et al. (2011)). The development of an experimental paradigm for visual fixation in tethered walking honeybees would allow for control of the visual stimuli presented to the eye and simultaneous recording from the brain, enabling studies of learning and memory, navigation, and attention. We show here that FicTrac is suitable for this purpose and, to demonstrate the versatility of our proposed ap-

proach, we also use FicTrac to demonstrate visual fixation in the fruit fly, *Drosophila melanogaster*.

2. Methods and preparation

The FicTrac software was written in C++ for Linux-based operating systems. Pre-compiled binaries for Ubuntu (Canonical Ltd.) are freely available for non-commercial use and can be downloaded from <http://bit.ly/fictrac>, along with installation prerequisites and instructions. FicTrac has also been tested successfully with the Windows 7 & 8 (Microsoft Corporation) operating systems by operating Ubuntu within a virtual machine (VMware Inc.).

2.1. Motion tracking

FicTrac computes the absolute 3-DOF orientation of a track ball by localising the currently visible portion of the sphere within a learned map of its entire surface. The surface map is created by stitching together frame-by-frame views of the sphere over time and thus does not need to be pre-computed because it is created ‘on the fly’ as the ball is rotated by the animal. The orientation of the sphere is localised independently each frame, which differs fundamentally from the typical optical mouse-based approach, where the orientation of the sphere is tracked over time by concatenating the entire sequence of measured 3-DOF rotations. However, in order to reconstruct the 2D trajectory of an animal tethered to a spherical treadmill, the absolute orientation of the sphere at any given instant in time is not immediately useful because infinitely many different sequences of rotations can produce the same resultant sphere orientation. By sampling the orientation of the sphere at a fast rate, however, the intended path of the animal on a fictive 2D surface can be tracked by integrating the change in orientation of the sphere about each of the animal’s principal axes (Figure 1).

FicTrac as well as the established optical mouse-based method thus both require integration of noisy measurements of the change in orientation of the sphere to reconstruct the path of the animal on a fictive 2D plane. Rotation rates derived from FicTrac are less susceptible to measurement bias than the corresponding optical mouse-based measurements however, because the underlying visual measurements of sphere orientation computed by FicTrac will not drift.

2.1.1. Pattern segmentation

The pattern on the surface of the sphere is segmented by FicTrac into a binary representation using a simple adaptive thresholding technique. The pattern may be composed of any two-colour scheme and does not need to be black and white. For non-grayscale patterns, the input region of interest (ROI) is converted to the luminance-chrominance (YUV) colour space and a distance transform is applied to the chrominance channels prior to thresholding. The distance transform computes the pseudo-distance in the 2D chrominance space between each pixel in the ROI and the YUV values of the foreground and background regions on the track ball, which are defined during the interactive configuration procedure. The computational cost incurred by

Figure 1: Diagram of the various components of our spherical treadmill and relevant coordinate axes. FicTrac measures rotation of the sphere in the camera’s coordinate frame, c , and transposes to the animal’s coordinate frame, a , to determine the animal’s walking (red), sidestepping (green), and yawing (blue) motions, which are integrated in the world coordinate frame, w , to obtain the animal’s 2D path on a fictive plane. Note that the ‘screen’ on which the track ball is projected is merely a visualisation of the camera’s image plane.

FicTrac is approximately constant regardless of the colouring scheme used, but binary patterns that are not distinct in either intensity or chrominance space will degrade the performance of the matching algorithm.

The pattern applied to the ball must also be non-repetitive so that each view of the sphere is distinct. A free drawn pattern of blobs (*e.g.* Figure 2a) was determined empirically to be sufficient to satisfy this criterion. Finer details enable more precise matching but require a higher resolution input ROI for them to be resolved, which increases execution time exponentially and reduces the robustness of the matching algorithm to large rotational displacements between frames. The trade-off between matching precision and execution speed is discussed further in section 5.1. Ideally, a mix of spatial frequencies should be used for fast and precise matching performance.

2.1.2. Projecting onto the model sphere

The orientation of the track ball is determined each frame by rotating a textured spherical model so that its appearance matches that of the track ball in the input ROI. Pixels in the input ROI are mapped to the surface of the model sphere using an ideal (fisheye or rectilinear) projection model for the camera (Figure 3).

The 3D coordinates of the points of intersection between the camera’s view vectors and the spherical model are computed using a quadratic factorisation of the equation for a sphere, $\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{c}\| = r$, and the equation for a 3D line, $\mathbf{x} = d \cdot \hat{\mathbf{l}}$; where \mathbf{x} is a point of intersection, \mathbf{c} is the centre of the sphere, r is the radius of the sphere, $\hat{\mathbf{l}}$ is a unit vector describing the direction of a line (*i.e.* view vector), and d is the distance from the camera’s nodal

Figure 2: Visual output from the FicTrac software (see supplementary video). (a) A segment of the raw input image, overlaid with a short path history of the animal on the surface of the track ball (cyan line); (b) fisheye projection of the segmented input region of interest (ROI); (c) disparity between the previous and current ROIs after warping the previous ROI using the estimated change in orientation between the two frames; (d) instantaneous geographic projection of the visible portion of the patterned sphere after localisation within the surface map of the sphere; (e) the animal’s two dimensional fictive path computed by FicTrac; and (f) the current state of the accumulated surface map.

point along the line, $\hat{\mathbf{l}}$, to the intersection point with the surface of the sphere. Solving for d and simplifying gives

$$d = (\hat{\mathbf{l}} \cdot \mathbf{c}) \pm \sqrt{(\hat{\mathbf{l}} \cdot \mathbf{c})^2 - c^2 + r^2}, \quad (1)$$

which can yield up to two solutions depending on whether the view vector misses, grazes, or punctures the spherical surface. Equation 1 can be simplified by arbitrarily defining the sphere centre, $\mathbf{c} = [0 \ 0 \ 1]^T$, which is equivalent to defining a virtual camera model with a principal axis directly aligned with the apparent centre of the track ball in the input ROI. The distance to the sphere along the virtual principal axis can be set to unity because the projection of a sphere onto the image plane

Figure 3: Diagram of the model sphere and its projection in the camera’s coordinate frame. The coordinate frames of the camera, c , and model sphere, s , are identical, except the model sphere’s coordinate frame is centred at $[0 \ 0 \ 1]^T$ in the reference frame of the camera. For each input video frame, candidate rotations (represented here as a change in orientation, $\Delta\Omega$) are applied to the textured model sphere until its projection matches the segmented input ROI. The surface map for the model sphere is actually stored as a geographic projection (Figure 2f), so that it may be represented as a rectangular image.

is indistinguishable from the projection of another sphere with the same distance-radius ratio. The spherical model can thus be described by its radius only, and Equation 1 can be re-written

$$d = \hat{l}_z \pm \sqrt{(\hat{l}_z)^2 - 1 + r^2}, \quad (2)$$

where \hat{l}_z represents the z component of a unit view vector, and the radius of the sphere, r , is determined by $r = \sin \theta_{1/2}$, where $\theta_{1/2}$ is the half angle subtended by the track ball in the input ROI. Thus, a view vector intersects the camera-facing hemisphere at the point, \mathbf{x} , with respect to the camera's coordinate frame, \mathbf{c} ,

$$\mathbf{x}^c = \left(\hat{l}_z - \sqrt{(\hat{l}_z)^2 - 1 + r^2} \right) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{c}}. \quad (3)$$

The set of 3D intersection points, $\{\mathbf{x}^c\}$, represents the projection of the pixels within the input ROI onto the surface of the model sphere.

2.1.3. Geographic mapping

In order to localise the current view of the track ball within the surface map of the model sphere, a candidate 3-DOF rotation, $\mathbf{\Omega}_i$, is applied to the intersection points, $\{\mathbf{x}\}$,

$$\{\mathbf{x}^s\}_i = \mathbf{\Omega}_i \times \{\mathbf{x}^s\}, \quad (4)$$

where the superscript, s , denotes that the intersection points must be given in the coordinate frame of the sphere, $\mathbf{x}^s = \mathbf{x}^c - \mathbf{c}^c$ (Figure 3).

A geographic projection (the equal-area cylindrical, or Gall-Peters, projection) is then used to map the input pixels corresponding to the set of candidate intersection points to a rectangular surface map (Figure 2d), such that rows and columns of pixels in the surface map image correspond to lines of equal latitude and longitude respectively on the model sphere. To score a candidate rotation, the sum of absolute disparity (SAD) is computed between all pixels in the candidate instantaneous projection of the track ball's surface and the corresponding pixels in the stored reference map (Figure 2f).

2.1.4. Localising 3-DOF orientation

The 3-DOF rotation, $\mathbf{\Omega}_{\min}$, that best minimises the SAD between the instantaneous geographic projection of the track ball's surface and the stored reference map is found using NLOpt's (Johnson, 2013) implementation of the BOBYQA gradient-free non-linear optimisation algorithm (Powell, 2009) with three parameters (an angle-axis formulation of the 3-DOF orientation of the sphere). This is an iterative procedure that essentially searches for the 3D rotation that best maps FicTrac's internal representation of the sphere onto the current view of the real sphere in the input ROI. The maximum number of candidate rotations that may be evaluated by the optimisation algorithm is clamped so that difficult matches will not cause large latencies. Typically, the optimisation algorithm terminates upon reaching the target error threshold. However, poor matches may be discarded by FicTrac and, if too many sequential frames are discarded, FicTrac may perform an exhaustive search of the

3D parameter space for the orientation of the sphere (this option may be disabled for closed-loop operation, in which case it is important to ensure that FicTrac is configured correctly and that adequate illumination is maintained throughout the experiment).

2.1.5. Updating the sphere

Once the orientation of the track ball has been estimated ($\mathbf{\Omega}_{\min}$), the reference surface map (Figure 2f) is updated with the current observations of the track ball's surface pattern. It was established empirically that a binary representation produced more stable maps than a continuous or greyscale average intensity representation, whilst still being fast to execute. Typically, the entire surface of the track ball is mapped and stabilised after a few seconds of walking by the animal. FicTrac does not therefore require an *a priori* map of the track ball, as the map can be built on the fly.

2.1.6. Transposing coordinate frames

To reproduce the motions of the tethered animal on a fictive 2D surface, the rotations of the sphere must be decomposed into rotations about each of the animal's coordinate axes. Thus, the rotational transformation between the coordinate frames of the model sphere and the animal must be known. The model sphere's coordinate frame was defined arbitrarily with respect to the camera frame (see section 2.1.2) and is therefore known to FicTrac, but the transformation between the reference frame of the camera and that of the animal is unknown as it depends on the relative orientation of those objects within the experimental enclosure. A novel procedure that was developed for estimating this transformation directly from the input imagery is described in Appendix A. This procedure is optional, however, if the rotational transformation between the camera and the animal subject can be measured independently.

2.1.7. Generating the fictive path

Once the orientation of the sphere, $\mathbf{\Omega}$, has been calculated relative to the animal's coordinate frame, a , its change in orientation between frames, $\Delta\mathbf{\Omega}^a$, specifies the rotational motion about each of the animal's coordinate axes,

$$\omega^a = \text{rodrigues}(\Delta\mathbf{\Omega}^a), \quad (5)$$

where the *rodrigues* function converts a 3×3 rotation matrix, $\mathbf{\Omega}$, to its 3×1 angle-axis formulation, ω , and vice-versa, according to Rodrigues' rotation formula (Belongie, 2013).

Rotations about the z (yaw) axis of the animal can be integrated to obtain the animal's heading direction in the current time frame, k ,

$$\Theta^k = \Theta^{k-1} - \omega_z. \quad (6)$$

Rotations about the remaining two orthogonal axes define the instantaneous walking vector for the animal (*i.e.* the magnitude and direction of the animal's motion with respect to its forward axis – the animal may not necessarily be walking forwards), which can be transformed into the world frame using the animal's current heading and then integrated to obtain the animal's

fictive 2D path,

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_x \\ P_y \end{bmatrix}^k = \begin{bmatrix} P_x \\ P_y \end{bmatrix}^{k-1} + \begin{bmatrix} \cos \Theta^k & -\sin \Theta^k \\ \sin \Theta^k & \cos \Theta^k \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \omega_y \\ -\omega_x \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Animal motion, including the fictive 2D path, is fundamentally computed by FicTrac in radians, but can be converted to units of distance simply using the equation for the length of a circular arc, $L = r\theta$, given the radius of the sphere, r .

2.2. Experimental setup and animal preparation

Experiments were conducted to test FicTrac’s performance at measuring the rotation of a spherical treadmill. A polystyrene ball (Spotlight Pty. Ltd.) (weight ~ 1.6 g and radius 25 mm) was patterned using a felt tip marker to provide orientation cues for FicTrac. Frictionless rotation of the track ball was achieved by supporting it on a stream of pressurised air, which was conducted to a hemispherical depression surrounding the ball through a custom 3D printed support structure (Plastic Ink Pty. Ltd.). Rotations of the ball were recorded at 30 Hz by a camera (Quickcam Pro 9000 (Logitech International S.A.) for calibration and open-loop experiments, and Firefly (Point Grey Research Inc.) for closed-loop experiments), and at 100 Hz by two optical mouse sensors (ADNS 7050 (Avago Technologies Ltd.) tracking sensor from MX400 laser computer mouse (Logitech International S.A.)). The optical mouse sensors were rigidly affixed to the support structure such that they faced the centre of the track ball, approximately 3 mm from its surface, and at 90° to each other in the horizontal plane normal to the sphere’s axis of rotation (Figure 4a). For behavioural experiments, the animal’s forward axis was offset 45° from both optical mouse sensors (Figure 4c). This is a commonly used configuration for measuring the rotation of a spherical treadmill using optical mouse sensors (Takalo et al., 2012; Clark et al., 2011; Hölscher et al., 2005).

2.2.1. Calibration setup

A calibrated stepper motor was used to rotate the track ball precisely about a single axis so that FicTrac’s performance under laboratory conditions could be evaluated and compared to the performance of a standard optical mouse-based approach.

A custom C++ program captured incremental motions from the optical mouse sensors at 100 Hz, which gave two 2D velocities, \mathbf{m}_1 and \mathbf{m}_2 , from which the instantaneous walking velocity, \mathbf{W}_m , and turning rate, ω_{mz} , in the animal’s reference frame were computed

$$\mathbf{W}_m = \alpha \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_a & -\sin \theta_a \\ \sin \theta_a & \cos \theta_a \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} m_{1y} \\ m_{2y} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

$$\omega_{mz} = \alpha \frac{m_{1x} + m_{2x}}{2 \cdot r}, \quad (9)$$

where r is the radius of the track ball, m_{nx} and m_{ny} are the horizontal and vertical components of motion respectively reported by the n^{th} optical mouse sensor, the rotation matrix in (8) preceding the measurement vector accounts for the angular offset between the orientation of the animal and that of the optical

(a) Raw input frame during calibration.

(b) Rendered frame.

(c) Tethered walking preparation for the honeybee.

Figure 4: The various experimental environments for this study. (a) A raw input frame from the ground truth testing, showing the 3D printed structure for housing the track ball and optical mouse sensors, as well as the metal pole inserted into the track ball and used to rotate it about its vertical axis during calibration; (b) a rendered frame from the simulated track ball rotation sequence; and (c) a photograph of the tethered walking preparation for the honeybee, showing track ball, optical mouse sensors, LED panels and visual stimulus, as well as a tethered animal (close-up in inset).

mouse forward axis (in this case $\theta_a = -45^\circ$, see Figure 4), and α is a calibration factor relating motion measured by the sensors (in pixels) to actual translation (in metric units). Heading direction, Θ_m , in the current frame, k , was then computed by integrating the turning rate,

$$\Theta_m^k = \Theta_m^{k-1} + \omega_{mz}. \quad (10)$$

and finally, the fictive path was reconstructed by transposing the instantaneous walking vector into the world coordinate frame and integrating,

$$\begin{bmatrix} P_{mx} \\ P_{my} \end{bmatrix}^k = \begin{bmatrix} P_{mx} \\ P_{my} \end{bmatrix}^{k-1} + \begin{bmatrix} \cos \Theta_m^k & -\sin \Theta_m^k \\ \sin \Theta_m^k & \cos \Theta_m^k \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} W_{mx} \\ W_{my} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

To enable fair comparisons between the optical mouse-based approach and FicTrac, the optical mouse data was downsampled to match the sampling rate used by FicTrac in each case (30 Hz for the calibration and honeybee experiments).

2.2.2. Behavioural experiments

Behavioural experiments with honeybees were conducted using a light emitting diode (LED) array (Shenzhen Sinorad Medical Electronics Inc.) arranged as a diamond (Figure 4c) similar to the setup described by Zhou et al. (2012). The LED array comprised four tri-colour 32 px \times 32 px panels, which covered 360° \times 54° of the animal’s azimuthal and vertical FOV respectively. Visual stimulation was generated using Vision Egg (Straw, 2008) at 200 Hz. The stimulus comprised a single bright vertical bar, which was presented to the animal using the LED array. Illuminated pixels representing the vertical bar were green ($\lambda = 518$ nm) and subtended a viewing angle of 20° \times 54° (12 px \times 32 px) at a peak luminance of 168 lux from the perspective of the animal; other pixels were not illuminated.

The animal was prepared by shaving its back with a scalpel and then attaching a thin metal L-shaped rod (the tether) to its thorax using wax (Figure 4c inset). The head was then secured to the thorax using dental cement (Synergy D6 FLOW A3.5/B3, Coltène/Whaledent AG). The tethered animal was then positioned accurately on top of the track ball using a 3-axis translation stage and a rotary adjuster. Walking and turning motions of the animal were conveyed to rotational motions of the track ball, which were in turn recorded by the optical mouse sensors and also by a video camera. Images captured by the camera at 30 Hz were processed by FicTrac to derive the motions and trajectory intended by the animal in response to the visual stimulus. Data from the optical mouse-based system, camera images, and the position of the stimulus were timestamped to enable direct comparison.

3. Results I: Ground truth testing

The accuracy of the proposed approach (FicTrac) was analysed quantitatively in simulation before its performance was compared to that of a standard optical mouse-based approach under laboratory conditions.

3.1. Simulated trials

A virtual sphere and a camera representing the real camera used with FicTrac were modelled and rendered using POV-Ray (Persistence of Vision Raytracer Pty. Ltd.) and a surface texture template (Figure 4b). Three rotation sequences were rendered and passed to FicTrac via its standard input method. For the first sequence the virtual track ball was rotated 360° (100 \times 3.6° steps) about its z axis. It was found that FicTrac accurately apportioned rotation of the virtual sphere to the z axis with very little off-axis rotation (Figure 5a). The absolute angular error grew as partly unseen regions of the sphere’s surface were added to the map sequentially (Figure 5b), but once the dynamically constructed map formed a closed path on the surface of the sphere, uncertainty in the orientation of the track ball became bounded and therefore did not continue to grow over time.

The second sequence simulated a virtual sphere rotating about a time-varying axis, eventually passing through its initial orientation (Figure 5c), and showed that the error in FicTrac’s estimate of the sphere’s orientation remained bounded

after multiple revolutions (Figure 5d). The maximum absolute angular error during the complex rotation sequence was 2.08°. FicTrac was *not* pre-loaded with a surface template for these tests, but when FicTrac was pre-loaded with a ground-truth surface map and the complex rotation test was repeated for comparison, no significant improvement in maximum absolute error was observed. This result indicated that the spherical surface map created dynamically by FicTrac was an adequate representation of the ground truth template (Figure 6), and thus FicTrac was able to accurately estimate the rotational displacement of the sphere without an *a priori* map.

The third and final sequence simulated a rotation of $\sqrt{17} \cdot 360^\circ$ about an axis of $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{4}{\sqrt{17}} & \frac{1}{\sqrt{17}} \end{bmatrix}$ in the coordinate frame of the virtual animal, which is the rotation that would have resulted from a tethered animal walking an exactly circular path of length 8π radians (Figure 5e). The absolute position error between the computed fictive path and the ground truth during the test (Figure 5f) was unbounded because the fictive 2D position of the animal was integrated from the measured instantaneous rotations of the track ball about each of the animal’s coordinate axes (Equation 7). However, the error between the computed fictive 2D position of the animal and ground truth grew slowly because the error associated with the measured rotation of the track ball itself was well bounded and small (Figure 5d).

3.2. Ground truth tests

A quantitative evaluation of both FicTrac and the optical mouse-based approach was performed by rotating the track ball about its z (yaw) axis at various constant speeds for a minimum of ten revolutions at each speed, using a calibrated stepper motor. For this calibration test only, the transformation from the camera’s reference frame to the laboratory (animal) reference frame was computed by finding the corrective rotation matrix that best aligned the measured axis of rotation with the z axis (averaged for all tested rotational speeds). The optical mouse calibration factor, α , was also determined empirically for this test by scaling the rotation rate measured by the optical mouse system about the laboratory z axis such that it matched the true rotation rate of the track ball (averaged for all tested rotational speeds).

We found that FicTrac measured the rotational velocity of the track ball more accurately and more precisely than the optical mouse-based approach (Figure 7a). In fact, the accuracy and precision metrics computed for the optical mouse data were approximately an order of magnitude worse than those computed for FicTrac, even though α was computed *a posteriori*. Furthermore, the normalised standard deviation ($\frac{\sigma}{\mu}$), or coefficient of variation (CV), for the FicTrac measurements decreased exponentially as the rotation rate was increased, indicating an approximately constant measurement variance, which was expected because FicTrac’s rotation rate estimates were derived from independent measurements of sphere orientation. In contrast, the precision of the optical mouse system did not improve appreciably at higher rotation rates, indicating that the standard deviation of the optical mouse measurements increased approximately in proportion to the rotational speed of the track ball.

Figure 5: Simulated trials. (a) Orientation (angle-axis) of the sphere measured by FicTrac during a single revolution about the z axis (note that the x trace is obscured by the y trace), and (b) the absolute angular error between FicTrac’s orientation estimate and ground truth. Maximum angular error was 1.25° and bounded after a complete revolution. (c) Orientation (angle-axis) and (d) absolute angular error measured during a complex rotation sequence. Maximum angular error was 2.08° and bounded. (e) Fictive 2D path computed by FicTrac from a circular walk showing (inset) disparity between the (green) start point and (red) computed end point, as well as (f) the absolute error between FicTrac’s 2D position estimate and ground truth. Ground truth circular path length was 8π radians. The final position error was 0.23 radians (0.92% of the total path length) and was unbounded because the 2D path was integrated from noisy rotation estimates – *i.e.* the path error would be expected to continue to grow at the same rate if the virtual animal continued along the same path. Units of radians are used (e – f) because those subplots show measurements of integrated position and associated error, rather than orientation.

To emphasise the benefit of deriving the rotational rate from independent estimates of orientation, the total absolute angular error at the conclusion of each trial was computed. FicTrac’s average angular error was 0.67° , or 0.02% of the total rotation. A similar measure could not be calculated for the optical mouse data because the approximation for absolute 3D angular error used here is only valid for small ($< 90^\circ$) errors.

In addition to measuring the rotational velocity accurately, minimising cross-talk between rotation axes is also impor-

(a) A surface map generated by FicTrac on the fly.

(b) Image difference between the FicTrac map and ground truth.

Figure 6: Mapping accuracy. (a) The map computed by FicTrac during a simulated trial and (b) a comparison with the template used to render the sphere. White regions represent disparity between the computed map and ground truth. The surface maps are represented by a geographic projection and correspond to 360° horizontally by 180° vertically. The approximate centre (b, green circle) of the tracking ROI at the beginning of the sequence corresponds to the region of minimum disparity between the dynamically generated map and ground truth. Mapping error increases outwards from this point, following the growth of the map, until previously mapped regions of the sphere are encountered.

Figure 7: Ground truth testing of FicTrac and the optical mouse system. (a) Average z -axis rotation rates measured via FicTrac (blue solid) and optical mouse (red dashed) normalised against ground truth from a minimum of 10 revolutions at various speeds; and (b) average unsigned magnitude (solid lines) and standard deviation (dashed lines) of the rotational velocity measured about the two off-axes (ideally there should be zero rotation measured about the x and y axes), normalised against ground truth for the same trials for FicTrac (blue circles) and optical mouse (red triangles). Error bars in (a) represent coefficient of variation (CV). FicTrac produced average unsigned error and CV at 0.22% and 5.55% of the ground truth speed, respectively. Optical mouse average unsigned error and CV were 3.50% and 32.0% respectively. FicTrac reported an average off-axis velocity error of 0.45% of ground truth with a CV of 4.40%. The same metrics for the optical mouse system were 1.58% and 10.3% respectively.

tant because it enables the fundamental motions of the animal (walking, sidestepping, and yawing) to be measured independently and accurately to provide a more accurate reconstruction of the animal’s behaviour. FicTrac reported about 70% less unwanted off-axis rotation than the optical mouse-based approach during the ground truth tests, although both methods reported an approximately constant percentage of off-axis rotation for

each of the tested rotational velocities (Figure 7b).

The results of the ground truth testing suggested that the sensitivity of the optical mouse sensor was subject to noise, leading to measurement variance that was approximately proportional to the rotation rate of the track ball. No such dependence was expected nor found with FicTrac. Optical mouse sensitivity (*i.e.* α) has been shown to depend on factors such as surface-sensor proximity, surface texture, surface patterning, and illumination (Minoni and Signorini, 2006; Ross et al., 2012; Chan et al., 2010). We found that these factors had a minor effect on the precision of our optical mouse-based approach, but they did affect the magnitude of the calibration factor, α (Appendix B). Ambient lighting and the position of the track ball were able to be controlled during the ground truth tests, which enabled a reasonably reliable calibration of the optical mouse sensors. However, calibrating the optical mouse sensors accurately under experimental conditions proved much more challenging. A more sophisticated experimental setup could have been designed to reduce the susceptibility of the optical mouse sensors to these environmental factors (*e.g.* Seelig et al. (2010)), but this only serves to highlight the simplicity of FicTrac’s approach and its robustness to a wide variety of experimental conditions.

4. Results II: Measurement of animal behaviour

To study the performance of FicTrac under experimental conditions, we measured the walking patterns of honeybees whilst they responded to visual stimuli. Two different experiments were conducted in which the bees were presented with a single bright bar. In the first experiment, the bees did not have control over the angular position of the bar (*i.e.* open-loop) and in the second experiment, the bees’ heading direction was measured and used to control the position of the bar directly (*i.e.* closed-loop). In both experiments, the animals’ motion was also recorded by our optical mouse sensor system for comparison with FicTrac. We show that FicTrac not only tracked the movements of the honeybees, but that measurements from the optical mouse sensors diverged substantially from the FicTrac results. We also show that FicTrac is efficient enough to enable closed-loop fixation to be performed by the walking honeybees.

4.1. Open-loop response to a visual stimulus in the honeybee

For the open-loop experiments, three honeybees were each exposed to an average of eight trials. During each trial, the stimulus was presented, in turn, at each of three static locations for 30 s each (directly ahead of the animal, or 45° to the left or right of centre, Figure 8b). Average turning rate data from both FicTrac and the optical mouse system clearly showed that each animal attempted to return the stimulus to the centre of her visual field when it was presented off-centre (Figure 9c), although the optical mouse system consistently underestimated the turning response of the animal compared to FicTrac (Figure 9a).

One-sample *t*-tests, computed on the average difference between the turning rates reported by FicTrac and the optical mouse system under each of the three stimulus conditions (Appendix C), showed that there was a significant difference between the average turning rates reported by the two approaches

(a) An example fictive path from the open-loop experiment.

(b) Detailed segments from the example fictive path.

Figure 8: (a) An example 2D fictive path estimated by FicTrac (black/blue/green solid) and the optical mouse-based system (red dashed) during three consecutive open-loop trials with a single honeybee, and (b) data segments from the same trials showing details of the path computed during the first 5 s following a change in stimulus. Coloured segments of the FicTrac path indicate periods when the static stimulus was positioned to the left (green), frontally (black), or to the right (blue) of the bee respectively. Paths were aligned at the start (yellow dot) of each segment to enable comparison. Individual axis scales in (b) indicate 10 mm.

Figure 9: Analysis of the effect of bar position on the behaviour of the honeybee, showing the average (a) turning rate and (b) walking pace measured by FicTrac (blue circles) and the optical mouse system (red triangles) under each of the three stimulus conditions (left/right = dashed lines, front = solid line) during each trial, as well as the total average (c) turning rate and (d) walking pace estimated by each measurement method for all trials. The general increase in average walking pace per trial is unexplained. Stars indicate significance (** $\rightarrow p < 0.01$; *** $\rightarrow p < 0.001$), and were computed using one-sample t -tests on the average difference between the two measurement methods under each stimulus condition (Appendix C). Also shown are the distributions of turning rates under each of the stimulus conditions during three trials from a single bee (corresponding to the open-loop path plotted in Figure 8a) measured by (c) FicTrac and (d) the optical mouse system.

when the stimulus was presented off-centre (Figure 9c). This difference could be attributed simply to a miscalibration of the optical mouse system – *i.e.* increasing the calibration factor, α , would have amplified the measured turning rate. However, increasing α would have also led to an increased sensitivity to walking speed, and the optical mouse system already significantly overreported the average walking speeds of the animals during the open-loop trials compared to the values measured by FicTrac (Figure 9b & d). The differences in the results produced by the two measurement techniques cannot, therefore, be cor-

rected by modifying the calibration factor for the optical mouse system and must be due instead to measurement biases.

Differences between the estimates of the animals' walking speeds measured by FicTrac and the optical mouse system led to an average difference in the estimated length of the path travelled by the animals during each trial of $71.5 \text{ cm} \pm 66.3 \text{ cm}$, or $\sim 15\%$ of the average path length computed by FicTrac. Furthermore, differences between the estimated turning rates led to very different reconstructions of the animals' fictive paths (*e.g.* Figure 8a). Segments of a single animal's fictive path, each comprising 5 s of data immediately following a change in the position of the stimulus, were analysed in detail (Figure 8b). The segments indicated agreement between the optical mouse-based method and FicTrac on the overall structure of the animal's trajectory, but the paths computed by FicTrac showed fewer discontinuities and qualitatively appeared to better represent the expected behaviour of the animal. Unfortunately, no quantitative appraisal of the two methods with respect to ground truth could be made due to the difficulty of obtaining ground truth data whilst an experiment was in progress. However, the comparisons with ground truth in the tests described in section 3.2 indicated that FicTrac is likely to be much more trustworthy.

An analysis of a single animal's turning rate during three consecutive open-loop trials revealed that the distributions of turning rates measured by FicTrac during each of the stimulus conditions were approximately Gaussian (Figure 9e), as expected. However, the distributions of turning rates measured by the optical mouse system during the same trials showed a clear bias for slower turning rates (Figure 9f). A random variation of the sensitivity, α , of the optical mouse system (*e.g.* due to ball texture) could explain both the dependence of measurement noise for that system on the speed of rotation of the track ball (Figure 7a) as well as the lopsided turning rate distributions measured via optical mouse (Figure 9f). However, such a variation does not fully explain the propensity for the optical mouse system to underestimate turning rate whilst overestimating walking pace. Further characterisation of the optical mouse system suggested that a patterned track ball may have led to axially asymmetric sensitivities in the optical mouse sensors, which would have contributed to the observed measurement bias (Appendix B). The bias may therefore have been reduced by calibrating the optical mouse axes independently. However, the reduced precision of the optical mouse system would still have led to lopsided sphere rotation rate measurement distributions (*e.g.* Figure 9f) and thus also produced fictive paths that diverged from FicTrac and ground truth.

4.2. Closed-loop visual fixation in the honeybee

During closed-loop experiments, changes in heading direction effected by the honeybees were measured by FicTrac and used to re-position the stimulus in real time. A unity gain was applied to the feedback – *i.e.* a recorded change in each honeybee's heading direction was reflected by an equal and opposite change to the azimuth of the stimulus within her visual field.

At random intervals ranging from 10 s – 60 s, the azimuthal position of the illuminated bar was displaced (or perturbed) to

increase the salience of the stimulus. Each displacement consisted of a translocation of the stimulus of approximately 90° applied over 0.3 s. All tested honeybees actively controlled the position of the bar and returned the stimulus to the centre of their visual field within approximately 1.5 s following the onset of the displacement (Figures 10a & 10b). Displacements were applied in either a clockwise or anti-clockwise manner, inducing right- or left-handed turns respectively.

The displacements caused the honeybees to make sharp turns of approximately 90° in magnitude, due to the unity feedback gain applied to the azimuthal position of the bar. The tightly clustered distribution of bar positions about the honeybees' forward axes during the closed-loop experiment (Figure 10c) demonstrated that the bees were in fact fixating on the stimulus and that they responded effectively to disturbances. The measured bias (15.4°) may have been due in part to the bees fixating on the edge of the 20° wide bar (Osorio et al., 1990). The roughly piecewise linear form of the fictive paths computed by FicTrac (Figure 10e) during visual fixation demonstrated that the bees were able to use the stimulus to follow a straight line trajectory, which would have been impossible without an absolute heading reference (Cheung et al., 2007). These results demonstrated that FicTrac was capable of accurately recording the instantaneous motions of a tethered animal under real experimental conditions and that these measurements were accurate enough for the system to faithfully represent the fictive 2D path of the animal. More importantly, these measurements were computed quickly enough to be used within a closed-loop experimental setup to provide real-time feedback for a behaving insect.

4.3. Closed-loop visual fixation in the fruit fly

To prove the versatility of FicTrac, it was applied to a separate experimental setup to demonstrate visual fixation with the fruit fly, *Drosophila melanogaster*. In this experiment, flies were prepared and tethered in a manner similar to that described in section 2.2.2 for the honeybee and stimulated using a cylindrical arrangement of 12 LED panels (Mettrix Technology Corporation) identical to that described by Reiser and Dickinson (2008) (Figure 11a). The flies were positioned on top of a patterned track ball, the motion of which was measured by FicTrac and used to re-position the stimulus in real time (*i.e.* closed-loop). The main differences from the experimental setup used for the honeybee were that the track ball was smaller (weight 37 mg and radius 7.5 mm), a red/black pattern (Figure 11a) was used to reduce the apparent contrast for the animal, and images were transmitted to FicTrac at a faster rate (60 Hz) using a firewire camera (A602f-2 (Basler AG) equipped with a 12 \times zoom lens (Navitar)).

The visual stimulus presented to the fly comprised a single vertical dark bar subtending a viewing angle of 20° azimuth and 54° elevation, which was presented against an illuminated green background. At random intervals ranging from 5 s – 10 s, the azimuthal position of the bar was displaced in either a clockwise or counter-clockwise direction by either 56° or 112° over a period of 1 s. The clustered distribution of bar positions about the fly's forward axis demonstrated that the animal effectively

Figure 10: Closed-loop honeybee behaviour with a single bright stimulus and unity gain for a population $n = 3$. (a) Animals' responses following an enforced clockwise displacement of the stimulus, and (b) a counter-clockwise displacement. The enforced displacements consisted of a $\sim 90^\circ$ shift over a period of 0.3 s. Coloured traces represent responses from individual trials. (c) Angular histogram of the position of the stimulus within the arena during the closed-loop experiment ($n = 3$), and (d) with an invisible stimulus (*i.e.* no visual feedback). The radial axes show bin count, for 2° bins. Closed-loop average stimulus position when visible (green circle) was $15.4^\circ \pm 71.6^\circ$, with a 95% confidence interval (including enforced displacements and associated responses). (e) An example fictive path computed by FicTrac during closed-loop fixation from a single bee. Periods of enforced (blue) clockwise (CW) or (red) counter-clockwise (CCW) displacement of the stimulus are highlighted. The example fictive path comprised a period of approximately 118 s during which the animal walked at an average pace of $36.6 \text{ mm/s} \pm 40.0 \text{ mm/s}$.

returned the bar to the centre of its visual field following a displacement (Figure 11b & c). These results show that FicTrac is able to be easily and usefully applied to a variety of experimental configurations.

Figure 11: Closed-loop fruit fly behaviour with a single dark stimulus and unity gain for a population $n = 1$. (a) A photograph of the tethered walking preparation for the fruit fly, showing the dark visual stimulus and illuminated LED panels, the red/black track ball and support structure, as well as the tethered animal. (b) Angular histogram of the position of the stimulus within the arena during the closed-loop experiment with the fruit fly. The radial axes show bin count, for 2° bins. Closed-loop average stimulus position (green circle) was $1.52^\circ \pm 118^\circ$, with a 95% confidence interval (including enforced displacements and associated responses). (c) Time plot of (black) the angular position of the bar as well as periods of (blue) clockwise and (red) counter-clockwise displacement during closed-loop visual fixation with the fruit fly. Data was collected from a single animal over a continuous period of 218 s.

5. Discussion

The novel approach we have described for tracking spherical motion and generating 2D fictive animal paths offers a simple and robust alternative to the standard optical mouse-based technique. Due to the difficulty in obtaining ground truth data for the orientation of the spherical treadmill during complex sequences of rotations, there is a dearth of published data on the accuracy of optical mouse-based systems under typical experimental conditions. In this study we have compared FicTrac against our own implementation of a standard optical mouse-based system and we compare both systems against several representative approaches here to give credence to our findings.

Lee and Zhou (2004) describe a dual-optical mouse-based system for measuring 3-DOF orientation of a sphere and report results that correspond to an unsigned angular error of $0.97^\circ = 1.94\%$ after a rotation of 50° about a single axis. This is comparable to the accuracy measured for our optical mouse system (3.5% velocity error), but both methods are eclipsed by FicTrac, which we have shown here enables 3-DOF orientation to be determined to within 0.02% of ground truth, after a rotation of 3600° about a static axis. Seelig et al. (2010) also describe a dual-optical mouse-based system in which the sensing axes are orthogonal, similar to the optical mouse-based approach described here. They do not quote absolute measurement errors

for their system, but they do show that their sensors produce a strongly linear ($R^2 = 0.99$) calibration curve over a range of rotation speeds. They quote an average variability in their calibration factor, α , of approximately 10%. For comparison, we computed the coefficient of variation for rotation rate reported by our optical mouse system to be 32.0%, and in the same experiment we found FicTrac’s precision to be 5.55%. Finally, Kumagai and Hollis (2011) describe a triple optical mouse-based system for measuring spherical motion in which the sensors are each separated by 45° . This sensing configuration would be expected to be more accurate and less susceptible to asymmetrical measurement biases than a dual sensor approach and indeed the authors report an average final error of $0.92^\circ = 0.26\%$ after a rotation of 360° about a static axis. However, this still falls short of FicTrac, which we found to be more than twice as accurate ($0.36^\circ = 0.1\%$) during a simulation of an identical test and an order of magnitude more accurate ($0.67^\circ = 0.02\%$) following a real-world rotation of 3600° about a static axis.

Intuitively, optical mouse-based systems should provide very accurate estimates of rotational velocity due to their typically high frame rate and fine motion sensitivity. They require accurate calibration, however, because the fundamental unit of measurement for those systems is arbitrary. During the course of our research, we have found that this calibration factor can vary even between sensor axes and is particularly sensitive to changes surface pattern and texture. If those parameters cannot be controlled precisely in the experimental setup, the performance of the optical mouse-based sensors can degrade significantly. FicTrac is superior to optical mouse-based systems in this regard because it is more robust to varying experimental conditions and also because it fundamentally computes the absolute orientation of the sphere rather than its surface linear velocity, which we have shown eliminates biases in the computation of rotational velocity. This enables FicTrac to recreate 2D fictive animal paths with greater accuracy than our low-cost optical mouse-based system.

Visual methods for computing the absolute orientation of a sphere have been proposed by others previously (*e.g.* Garner et al. (2001); Stein et al. (2003); Wang et al. (2010)). However, in all of these approaches the surface pattern must be known by the decoder *a priori*. The advantage of FicTrac over these approaches is that the surface map is learned on the fly, which significantly reduces the effort required to implement the system. Furthermore, FicTrac’s matching algorithm is very efficient, which allows it to be used for low-latency applications such as providing sensory feedback for behavioural experiments with insects.

5.1. Limitations

The main limitations of the proposed visual tracking system are that it requires the spherical track ball to be textured with a high-contrast pattern, and that the temporal frequency and latency of FicTrac’s estimates for the orientation of the sphere and the motion of the animal are typically limited by the frame rate of the camera. These issues and others that affect FicTrac’s performance are discussed below.

5.1.1. Temporal frequency and latency

Due to the image processing and matching algorithms employed by FicTrac, execution time increases exponentially with the tracking ROI resolution (Figure 12). At a typical quality setting, $Q = 6$, the resolution of the tracking ROI is $60 \text{ px} \times 60 \text{ px}$ and FicTrac’s latency is 10.7 ms (Table 1)³, which is relatively minor compared to the overall latency of the system measured during the closed-loop experiments with the honeybee ($87 \text{ ms} \pm 16 \text{ ms}$). For comparison, the measured latency of the optical mouse system for the same experimental configuration was $46 \text{ ms} \pm 8 \text{ ms}$. The disparity between the two approaches was due largely to the transmission time of the camera (usually the limiting factor for maximum frame rate), which could have been reduced by using a higher bandwidth connection (such as the firewire connection used during demonstration of visual fixation in the fruit fly), or by reducing the input image dimensions or bit depth.

Figure 12: FicTrac execution times and image matching errors following minimisation for various quality factors. Quality factor, Q , encodes the resolution of the tracking ROI and surface map. For an input image resolution $\sim 640 \text{ px} \times 480 \text{ px}$, $Q < 3$ is insufficient for matching and $Q \sim 20$ represents the maximum possible resolution of the tracking ROI. Execution times were computed on a 3.1 GHz processor.

For both the honeybee and the fruit fly closed-loop experiments, FicTrac and the stimulus display program (Vision Egg (Straw, 2008) for the honeybee and a custom Matlab (The Mathworks Inc.) script (Reiser and Dickinson, 2008) for the fruit fly) were executed within the Ubuntu 12.10 (Canonical Ltd.) operating system. The transfer of data from FicTrac to the stimulus display program was performed in each case using a shared file system, which led to significant latencies ($\sim 15 \text{ ms}$). This source of latency for closed-loop experiments has since been eliminated by enabling FicTrac to output data via network sockets. Regardless, we have shown in this study that the additional latency introduced by FicTrac is small enough to demonstrate closed-loop visual fixation in the honeybee and fruit fly.

5.1.2. Track ball texture

A high-contrast binary pattern must be applied to the surface of the track ball in order for FicTrac to measure its rotation. Black/white patterns (*e.g.* Figure 2) were determined empirically to provide the best contrast under various lighting conditions. However, combinations such as red/black (Figure 11a)

³In fact, FicTrac’s average frame rate under these conditions is usually slightly faster because the ROI segmentation can be performed in parallel to the other processes on a multi-core processor.

Table 1: Typical breakdown of system latency for 3.1 GHz processor, USB camera @ 30 Hz VGA, and FicTrac quality setting $Q = 6$. Vision Egg latency is given by Straw (2008). Latency breakdown for the optical mouse system is also shown for comparison.

Component	Latency (ms)	
	FicTrac	Mouse
Camera / input		
Exposure	< 1	n/a
Transmission	~ 33	$\ll 1$
FicTrac / optical mouse		
ROI segmentation	3.5	n/a
Matching / integration	6.8	< 11
Data output	0.4	< 1
Display		
Import data	~ 15	
Draw stimulus (Vision Egg)	< 30	
Total	87 ± 16	46 ± 8

and blue/yellow have also been tested successfully and may reduce the motion stimulus perceived by the animal subject. Motion of the sphere may also be shielded from the animal by separating the two with a sheet of paper or similar material, with a small circular opening to permit physical contact between the animal and the surface of the sphere. With this experimental configuration, the camera should be placed beneath the sheet of paper to ensure a sufficient proportion of the sphere is visible to FicTrac.

5.1.3. Camera-animal coordinate frame transformation

Uncertainty in FicTrac’s estimate of the sphere’s orientation is bounded because FicTrac computes the absolute orientation independently for each input frame. However, uncertainty in the reconstructed position of the animal on an imaginary 2D plane is not bounded because the animal’s fictive path is integrated from noisy estimates of the sphere’s rotation rate in the animal’s coordinate frame. A possible source of bias during integration of the spherical rotation rates is in the transformation between the camera and animal coordinate frames. If this transformation is not applied accurately (either because it is misspecified or because the animal is not positioned accurately at the top of the sphere), measured rotations of the tracking sphere will be incorrectly apportioned to the animal’s movement and rotation axes. The transformation can be computed accurately by carefully measuring the position and orientation of the animal’s coordinate axes with respect to the camera’s coordinate frame, either manually or by using the interactive configuration procedure that was developed specifically for this purpose (Appendix A).

5.2. Other applications

In this article we have considered a specific application of FicTrac to the problem of recording fictive paths of teth-

ered animals. FicTrac is being applied to tracking the paths of tethered honeybees (*Apis mellifera*), fruit flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*), and fiddler crabs (*Uca vomeris*) in works in progress at various laboratories at the Queensland Brain Institute. The simplicity of the system and its generality make it suitable for use in any situation where the absolute or relative orientation of a sphere or its 3-DOF rotation rate must be measured. Other examples include encoding the motion of an omnidirectional wheel drive (e.g. Lauwers et al. (2006)), a feedback mechanism for the classical ball-plate problem (Li and Canny, 1993), or perhaps even determining the position of a satellite in orbit about the Earth.

6. Conclusion

We have introduced a novel system, FicTrac, for estimating the orientation of a sphere from visual input and described applications of this system for tracking the fictive paths of tethered honeybees and fruit flies during controlled stimulation. We have characterised the accuracy and robustness of our system and shown that it outperforms a low-cost implementation of the standard optical mouse-based approach to fictive path tracking. FicTrac’s superiority in this case stems from its ability to estimate the orientation of a sphere independently each frame, which leads to negligible measurement bias during computation of the rotation of the sphere and thus eliminates the artefactual cross-axis couplings as well as the cumulative position errors that are introduced by mouse sensors.

FicTrac requires minimal customisation by the experimenter and may be implemented in a wide variety of experimental configurations. Importantly, we have shown that FicTrac operates fast enough to provide real-time sensory feedback for a behaving insect, enabling studies on sensory responsiveness, learning and memory, and the neural mechanisms underpinning sensory processing, to name but a few. We hope that FicTrac will enable simpler experimental setups and lead to studies that further our understanding of animal behaviour.

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Appendix A. Estimating the animal’s coordinate frame

In order for FicTrac’s estimates of the sphere’s rotation to be useful, they must be transformed into the coordinate frame of the animal. This transformation depends precisely on the relative position and orientation of the camera and animal. An interactive configuration procedure was developed to estimate the transformation automatically, which relied upon estimating the orientation of a 2D square from its projection onto the camera’s image plane. If the square’s normal vector is parallel with the z (yaw) axis of the animal and the sides of the square are aligned with the x (forward) and y (right) axes of the animal, then the estimated orientation of the square uniquely defines the coordinate axes for the animal in the coordinate frame of the camera.

During the interactive configuration procedure the user specifies two points lying along each side of the square in an image captured by the camera. The 3D orientation and 3D translation (up to a scale factor) of the square with respect to the origin of the camera’s coordinate frame are then determined by minimising the image-space disparity between the computed locations of the square’s corners and the projected corners of a model square, using a non-linear optimisation strategy (Johnson, 2013; Powell, 2009).

Appendix B. Optical mouse error analysis

We found that the sensitivity of the optical mouse sensors was susceptible to environmental conditions (see section 3.2). Two additional experiments were conducted in an attempt to identify which environmental factors were most influential. The track ball was rotated at a constant speed about a static axis for a period of approximately 20 s for each test case and statistics on the measured rotation rate were recorded. We found that varying the proximity of the optical mouse sensor to the surface of the track ball over the range 2 mm \rightarrow 6 mm caused a maximum variation in sensitivity of approximately 42% of the average rotation rate measured at each of the tested proximities (data not shown). However, sensitivity was directly compensated for by the calibration factor, α . The precision of the optical mouse sensor (Figure B.13a) was not greatly affected by proximity to the surface of the track ball over the range at which experimental data was collected (2 mm \sim 4 mm), although CV increased markedly once the separation between the sensor and the surface of the track ball was increased beyond 5 mm, indicating a loss in precision. Varying experimental conditions such as the level of ambient lighting, ball patterning, and ball colour caused a maximum variation in sensitivity of approximately 14% of the average rotation rate measured under each of the tested conditions (data not shown). A purely black track ball was found to improve the precision of the optical mouse sensors by approximately 11% over the binary pattern used in this work (Figure B.13b), however a solid colour track ball would not be compatible with FicTrac.

To further explore the measurement bias that affected the optical mouse system during the open-loop experiments (section 4.1), we tested the sensitivity of a single optical mouse

Figure B.13: Analyses of various noise processes for the optical mouse sensor, showing (a) sensitivity of the coefficient of variation (CV) to changes in surface-sensor proximity; (b) sensitivity to surface texture and ambient lighting; and (c) intrinsic sensitivity to the direction of tangential motion of the track ball surface (error bounds represent CV). Note that individual traces in (c) have been normalised by the magnitude of the sinusoid fitted to the data for each axis and that the CV has been suppressed for the horizontal axis at 0° and the vertical axis at 90° because CV is poorly defined for very small mean data values. Also shown is (d) the difference between the estimated direction of tangential motion and ground truth for each of the tested directions and track ball surface patterns.

sensor to the direction of the tangential motion of the track ball surface with respect to the two measurement axes of the sensor. Previous studies have found that the angle of motion of the substrate relative to the sensor axes is not always measured faithfully by the sensor (Palacin et al., 2006). We compared the motion measured along both sensor axes with the expected values for directions of tangential motion over the range $0 \rightarrow 180^\circ$. The motions measured along each measurement axis matched the expected values well (Figure B.13c).

The relative sensitivities of the optical mouse sensor's two axes were computed by comparing the relative magnitudes of the sinusoidal curves that were fitted to the rotation rates measured along each measurement axis at each direction of tangential rotation. The variation in sensitivity (or equivalently, the variation in average measured rotation rate) between the two sensor axes in the tested optical mouse sensor amounted to approximately 7% of the mean recorded rotation rate, for a patterned sphere. This asymmetry in sensitivity caused tangential directions of motion that were close to the sensor's vertical axis ($< 45^\circ$ or $> 135^\circ$) to be biased towards 0° or 180° respectively, effectively suppressing the minor axis for tangential directions of motion closely aligned with the vertical (corresponding to

0° and 180°) axis (Figure B.13d). A similar suppression of the minor axis was not observed for horizontal motions.

To test whether the sensitivity asymmetry between measurement axes was due to external conditions, the sensitivity versus direction of tangential motion experiment was repeated for an un-patterned (white) track ball and a solid black track ball (Figures B.13c & B.13d). The solid black track ball performed best with a sensor axial asymmetry of approximately 2%, and no apparent measurement biases. Surprisingly, the plain white track ball exhibited the largest CV (Figure B.13b) and also the largest axial asymmetry (8% of the mean recorded rotation rate).

Appendix C. Open-loop data statistical analysis

Open-loop turning rate and walking pace data was collected under three different stimulus conditions, using the experimental setup described in section 2.2.2 and using the experimental paradigm described in section 4.1. Comparisons between FicTrac and the optical mouse-based approach were made using one-sample *t*-tests (each with 23 degrees of freedom) to test the hypothesis that the average difference between the two measurement techniques was different from zero for each of the three stimulus conditions (Figure C.14 and Table C.2). Each sample point (average difference between turning rate or walking pace computed by FicTrac and the optical mouse-based approach during a single trial) was assumed not to depend on the animal nor on the order of presentation of the corresponding trial. Statistics were performed using SPSS V20 (IBM Corporation).

Figure C.14: Average difference between (a) rotation rate and (b) walking pace measured by FicTrac and the optical mouse system for each stimulus condition during the open loop trials. Error bars represent the standard deviations of the differences across the trials. Stars indicate significance (** $\rightarrow p < 0.01$; *** $\rightarrow p < 0.001$).

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Table C.2: Behavioural statistics in response to the three open-loop stimuli

Behaviour	Stimulus	<i>t</i> -test statistic	<i>p</i> value
Turn rate (°/s)	left	-8.23	$< 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$
	front	0.82	0.419
	right	13.4	$< 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$
Pace (mm/s)	left	-3.35	3.0×10^{-3}
	front	-12.4	$< 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$
	right	-10.2	$< 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$

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